

Biflavonyl Pigments from *Thuja plicata* (Cupressaceae)

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In continuation of our interest^{1,2} in the biflavonyl pigments of the cupressaceae, we wish to report the results of our investigations on the leaf extract of *Thuja plicata*.

The phenolic extractives of the leaves of *T. plicata* were separated by column chromatography on magnesium silicate followed by preparative TLC on silica gel to give two homogeneous components.

The first component m.p. $> 300^\circ$, Mol. wt. 538 (M^+) gave a hexa-acetate m.p. $229^\circ-230^\circ$, Mol. wt. 790 (M^+) and a hexamethyl ether m.p. 225° , Mol. wt. 622 (M^+). It was characterized as amentoflavone³ (I) by NMR studies.

Further support for its identity as amentoflavone was confirmed by the comparison of the NMR, IR, UV and Mass spectra of its acetate and methyl ether with authentic samples.

The second component m.p. $> 330^\circ$, Mol. wt. 537 (M^+) gave a pentaacetate m.p. $240^\circ-241^\circ$, and a pentamethyl ether m.p. $268^\circ-270^\circ$. It was characterized as hinokiflavane³ (II) by NMR studies.

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